

Strelitzia caudata Mountain strelitzia

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

Phylum: Magnoliophyta

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Estimated genome size: 739 million DNA base pairs (0.74 Gigabases)

Organism size: Up to 8 meters in height

Distribution:

The mountain strelitzia occurs from the Chimanimani Mountains in Zimbabwe, through Mozambique, the Northern Provinces of South Africa and Eswatini. It grows inland, preferring wetter habitats like Afromontane forests.

Importance:

The mountain strelitzia or wild banana is an impressive banana-like plant. It has unique white flowers with a pink tinge emerging from a purple spathe (sheath). It is one of three large *Strelitzia* species, alongside *Strelitzia alba* and *Strelitzia nicolai*, which are often confused.

PromethION Sequencing Report: Output: 47.59 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 9.11 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Genome length: 586.36 million bases (0.59 Gigabases)

BUSCO completeness score (single and duplicated genes): 98.9%

[Single: 56.5%, Duplicated: 42.4%]

Sample Contributor contact details

Prof. Eshchar Mizrachi

University of Pretoria

eshchar.mizrachi@fabi.up.ac.za

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